

ISic3695

I.Sicily inscription 3695

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

limestone

Object

stele

(?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

in re-use in the Hellenistic walls

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Megara Hyblaia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330076

1. [— —]εράτο ²⁷Ερατό(?) (Guarducci)²⁷.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 330076

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3695. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388972>